

α Generalized Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract: In this paper a new concept of neutrosophic closed sets called neutrosophic α generalized closed sets is introduced and their properties are thoroughly studied and analyzed. Some new interesting theorems based on the newly introduced set are presented.

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1. Introduction

The concept of neutrosophic sets was first introduced by Florentin Smarandache [3] in 1999 which is a generalization of intuitionistic fuzzy sets by Atanassov [1]. A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi [6] introduced the concept of neutrosophic topological spaces after Coker [2] introduced intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces. Further the basic sets like semi open sets, pre open sets, α open sets and semi- α open sets are introduced in neutrosophic topological spaces and their properties are studied by various authors [4,5]. The purpose of this paper is to introduce and analyze a new concept of neutrosophic closed sets called neutrosophic α generalized closed sets.

2. Preliminaries:

Here in this paper the neutrosophic topological space is denoted by (X, τ) . Also the neutrosophic interior, neutrosophic closure of a neutrosophic set A are denoted by $NInt(A)$ and $NCl(A)$. The complement of a neutrosophic set A is denoted by $C(A)$ and the empty and whole sets are denoted by 0_N and 1_N respectively.

Definition 2.1: Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set (NS) A is an object having the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $\mu_A(x)$, $\sigma_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(x)$ represent the degree of membership, degree of indeterminacy and the degree of non-

membership respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

A Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ can be identified as an ordered triple $\langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \nu_A \rangle$ in $]0, 1^+[$ on X .

Definition 2.2: Let $A = \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \nu_A \rangle$ be a NS on X , then the complement $C(A)$ may be defined as

1. $C(A) = \{ \langle x, 1 - \mu_A(x), 1 - \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$
2. $C(A) = \{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$
3. $C(A) = \{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$

Note that for any two neutrosophic sets A and B ,

4. $C(A \cup B) = C(A) \cap C(B)$
5. $C(A \cap B) = C(A) \cup C(B)$

Definition 2.3: For any two neutrosophic sets $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ we may have

1. $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x) \forall x \in X$
2. $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \geq \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x) \forall x \in X$
3. $A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \nu_A(x) \vee \nu_B(x) \rangle$
4. $A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x), \nu_A(x) \vee \nu_B(x) \rangle$
5. $A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x), \nu_A(x) \wedge \nu_B(x) \rangle$
6. $A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \nu_A(x) \wedge \nu_B(x) \rangle$

Definition 2.4: A neutrosophic topology (NT) on a non-empty set X is a family τ of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfies the following axioms:

- (NT₁) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau$
- (NT₂) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \tau$
- (NT₃) $\cup G_i \in \tau \forall \{ G_i : i \in J \} \subseteq \tau$

In this case the pair (X, τ) is a neutrosophic topological space (NTS) and any neutrosophic set in τ is known as a neutrosophic open set (NOS) in X . A neutrosophic set A is a neutrosophic closed set (NCS)

if and only if its complement $C(A)$ is a neutrosophic open set in X .

Here the empty set (0_N) and the whole set (1_N) may be defined as follows:

$$(0_1) \quad 0_N = \{\langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X\}$$

$$(0_2) \quad 0_N = \{\langle x, 0, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X\}$$

$$(0_3) \quad 0_N = \{\langle x, 0, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X\}$$

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$$(1_4) \quad 1_N = \{\langle x, 1, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X\}$$

Definition 2.5: Let (X, τ) be a NTS and $A = \{\langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$ be a NS in X . Then the neutrosophic interior and the neutrosophic closure of A are defined by

$$NInt(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is an NOS in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$$

$$NCl(A) = \cap \{K : K \text{ is an NCS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$$

Note that for any NS A , $NCl(C(A)) = C(NInt(A))$ and $NInt(C(A)) = C(NCl(A))$.

Definition 2.6: A NS A of a NTS X is said to be

- (i) a neutrosophic pre-open set (NP-OS) if $A \subseteq NInt(NCl(A))$
- (ii) a neutrosophic semi-open set (NS-OS) if $A \subseteq NCl(NInt(A))$
- (iii) a neutrosophic α -open set ($N\alpha$ -OS) if $A \subseteq NInt(NCl(NInt(A)))$
- (iv) a neutrosophic semi- α -open set (NS_{α} -OS) if $A \subseteq NCl(\alpha NInt(A))$

Definition 2.7: A NS A of a NTS X is said to be

- (i) A neutrosophic pre-closed set (NP-CS) if $NCl(NInt(A)) \subseteq A$
- (ii) A neutrosophic semi-closed set (NS-CS) if $NInt(NCl(A)) \subseteq A$
- (iii) A neutrosophic α -closed set ($N\alpha$ -CS) if $NCl(NInt(NCl(A))) \subseteq A$
- (iv) A neutrosophic semi- α -closed set (NS_{α} -CS) if $NInt(\alpha NCl(A)) \subseteq A$

3. α generalized closed sets in neutrosophic topological spaces

In this section we introduce neutrosophic α closure, neutrosophic α interior and α generalized closed set and its respective open set in neutrosophic topological spaces and discuss some of their properties.

Definition 3.1: A NS A in a NTS X is said to be a neutrosophic regular closed set (NRCS) if

$NCl(NInt(A)) = A$ and neutrosophic regular open set if $NInt(NCl(A)) = A$.

Definition 3.2: A NS A in a NTS X is said to be a neutrosophic β closed set ($N\beta$ CS) if $NInt(NCl(NInt(A))) \sqcap A$ and neutrosophic β open set if $A \sqcap NCl(NInt(NCl(A)))$

Definition 3.3: Let A be a NS of a NTS (X, τ) . Then the neutrosophic α interior and the neutrosophic α closure are defined as

$$N_{\alpha}Int(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is a } N\alpha\text{-OS in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$$

$$N_{\alpha}Cl(A) = \cap \{K : K \text{ is a } N\alpha\text{-CS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$$

Result 3.4: Let A be a NS in X . Then $N_{\alpha}Cl(A) = A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A)))$.

Proof: Since $N_{\alpha}Cl(A)$ is a $N\alpha$ -CS, $NCl(NInt(NCl(N_{\alpha}Cl(A)))) \subseteq N_{\alpha}Cl(A)$ and $A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A))) \subseteq A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(N_{\alpha}Cl(A)))) \subseteq A \cup N_{\alpha}Cl(A) = N_{\alpha}Cl(A)$ -----(i). Now

$NCl(NInt(NCl(A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A))))) \subseteq NCl(NInt(NCl(A \cup NCl(A)))) = NCl(NInt(NCl(NCl(A)))) = NCl(NInt(NCl(A))) \subseteq A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A)))$. Therefore $A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A)))$ is a $N\alpha$ -CS in X and hence

$N_{\alpha}Cl(A) \subseteq A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A)))$ -----(ii). From (i) and (ii), $N_{\alpha}Cl(A) = A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A)))$.

Definition 3.5: A NS A in a NTS X is said to be a neutrosophic α generalized closed set ($N_{\alpha g}$ CS) if $N_{\alpha}Cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is a NOS in X . The complement $C(A)$ of a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS A is a $N_{\alpha g}$ OS in X .

Example 3.6: Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, 1_N\}$ where $A = \langle x, (0.5, 0.6), (0.3, 0.2), (0.4, 0.1) \rangle$ and $B = \langle x, (0.4, 0.4), (0.4, 0.3), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle$. Then τ is a NT. Here $\mu_A(a) = 0.5$, $\mu_A(b) = 0.6$, $\sigma_A(a) = 0.3$, $\sigma_A(b) = 0.2$, $\nu_A(a) = 0.4$ and $\nu_A(b) = 0.1$. Also $\mu_B(a) = 0.4$, $\mu_B(b) = 0.4$, $\sigma_B(a) = 0.4$, $\sigma_B(b) = 0.3$, $\nu_B(a) = 0.5$ and $\nu_B(b) = 0.4$. Let $M = \langle x, (0.5, 0.4), ((0.4, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5)) \rangle$ be any NS in X . Then $M \subseteq A$ where A is a NOS in X . Now $N_{\alpha}Cl(M) = M \cup C(B) = C(B) \subseteq A$. Therefore M is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in X .

Proposition 3.7: Every NCS A is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in X but not conversely in general.

Proof: Let $A \subseteq U$ where U is a NOS in X . Now $N_{\alpha}Cl(A) = A \cup NCl(NInt(NCl(A))) \subseteq A \cup NCl(A) = A \cup A = A \subseteq U$, by hypothesis. Therefore A is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in X .

Example 3.8: In Example 3.6, M is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in X but not a NCS in X as $NCl(M) = C(B) \neq M$.

Remark 3.9: Every NS-CS and every $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in a NTS X are independent to each other in general.

Example 3.10: In Example 3.6, M is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS but not a NS-CS as $NInt(NCl(M)) = B \not\subseteq M$.

Example 3.11: Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, C, 1_N\}$, where $A = \langle x, (0.5, 0.4), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.6) \rangle$, $B = \langle x, (0.8, 0.7), (0.4, 0.3), (0.2, 0.3) \rangle$ and $C = \langle x, (0.2, 0.1), (0.3, 0.2), (0.8, 0.9) \rangle$. Then τ is a NT. Let $M = \langle x, (0.5, 0.3), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.7) \rangle$. Then M is a NS-CS but not a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS as $M \subseteq A, B$ and $N_{\alpha}Cl(M) = M \cup C(A) = C(A) \not\subseteq M$.

Remark 3.12: Every NP-CS and every $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in a NTS X are independent to each other in general.

Example 3.13: In Example 3.11, M is a NP-CS but not a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS as seen in the respective example.

Example 3.14: Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, 1_N\}$, where $A = \langle x, (0.5, 0.4), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.6) \rangle$ and $B = \langle x, (0.4, 0.3), (0.3, 0.1), (0.6, 0.7) \rangle$. Then τ is a NT. Let $M = \langle x, (0.5, 0.5), (0.2, 0.1), (0.4, 0.4) \rangle$. Then M is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS but not a NP-CS as $NCl(NInt(M)) = C(A) \not\subseteq M$.

Proposition 3.15: Every $N\alpha$ -CS A is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in X but not conversely in general.

Proof: Let $A \subseteq U$, where U is a NOS in X . Then $N_{\alpha}Cl(A) = A \subseteq NCl(NInt(NCl(A))) \subseteq A \subseteq A = A \subseteq U$, by hypothesis. Hence A is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in X .

Example 3.16: In Example 3.6, M is a $N_{\alpha g}$ -CS in X but not a $N\alpha$ -CS as $NCl(NInt(NCl(M))) = C(B) \not\subseteq M$.

Proposition 3.17: Every NOS, $N\alpha$ -OS are $N_{\alpha g}$ OS but not conversely in general.

Proof: Obvious.

Example 3.18: In Example 3.6, $C(M)$ is a $N_{\alpha g}$ OS but not a NOS, $N\alpha$ -OS in X .

Remark 3.19: Both NS-OS and NP-OS are independent to $N_{\alpha g}$ OS in X in general.

Example 3.20: The above Remark can be proved easily from the Examples 3.10, 3.11 and 3.13, 3.14 respectively.

Proposition 3.21: The union of any two $N_{\alpha g}$ CSs is a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS in a NTS X .

Proof: Let A and B be any two $N_{\alpha g}$ CSs in a NTS X . Let $A \subseteq B \subseteq U$ where U is a NOS in X . Then $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq U$. Now $N_{\alpha}Cl(A \cup B) = (A \cup B) \subseteq NCl(NInt(NCl(A \cup B))) \subseteq (A \cup B) \subseteq NCl(NCl(A \cup B)) \subseteq (A \cup B) \subseteq NCl(A \cup B) \subseteq NCl(A \cup B) = NCl(A) \cup NCl(B) \subseteq U \subseteq U = U$, by hypothesis. Hence $A \cup B$ is a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS in X .

Remark 3.22: The intersection of any two $N_{\alpha g}$ CSs need not be a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS in a NTS X .

Example 3.23: Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, 1_N\}$ where $A = \langle x, (0.5, 0.4), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.6) \rangle$ and $B = \langle x, (0.8, 0.7), (0.3, 0.2), (0.2, 0.3) \rangle$. Then τ is a NT. Let $M = \langle x, (0.6, 0.9), (0.3, 0.2), (0.4, 0.1) \rangle$ and $N = \langle x, (0.9, 0.7), (0.3, 0.2), (0.1, 0.3) \rangle$. Then M and N are $N_{\alpha g}$ CSs in X but $M \cap N = \langle x, (0.6, 0.7), (0.3, 0.2), (0.4, 0.3) \rangle$ is not a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS as $M \cap N \subseteq B$ and $N_{\alpha}Cl(M \cap N) = 1_N \not\subseteq A$.

Proposition 3.24: Let (X, τ) be a NTS. Then for every $A \in N_{\alpha g}C(X)$ and for every $B \in NS(X)$, $A \subseteq B \subseteq N_{\alpha}Cl(A)$ implies $B \in N_{\alpha g}C(X)$.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq U$ and U be a NOS in (X, τ) . Then since $A \subseteq B$, $A \subseteq U$. By hypothesis, $B \subseteq N_{\alpha}Cl(A)$. Therefore $N_{\alpha}Cl(B) \subseteq N_{\alpha}Cl(N_{\alpha}Cl(A)) = N_{\alpha}Cl(A) \subseteq U$, since A is an $N_{\alpha g}$ CS in (X, τ) . Hence $B \in N_{\alpha g}C(X)$.

Proposition 3.25: If A is a NOS and a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS in (X, τ) , then A is a $N\alpha$ -CS in (X, τ) .

Proof: Since $A \subseteq A$ and A is a NOS in (X, τ) , by hypothesis, $N_{\alpha}Cl(A) \subseteq A$. But $A \subseteq N_{\alpha}Cl(A)$. Therefore $N_{\alpha}Cl(A) = A$. Hence A is a $N\alpha$ -CS in (X, τ) .

Proposition 3.26: Let (X, τ) be a NTS. Then every NS in (X, τ) is a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS in (X, τ) if and only if $N\alpha$ -O(X) = $N\alpha$ -C(X).

Proof: Necessity: Suppose that every NS in (X, τ) is a $N_{\alpha g}$ CS in (X, τ) . Let $U \in NO(X)$. Then $U \in N\alpha$ -O(X) and by hypothesis, $N_{\alpha}Cl(U) \subseteq U \subseteq N_{\alpha}Cl(U)$. This implies $N_{\alpha}Cl(U) = U$. Therefore $U \in N\alpha$ -C(X). Hence $N\alpha$ -O(X) \subseteq $N\alpha$ -C(X). Let $A \in N\alpha$ -C(X). Then $C(A) \in N\alpha$ -O(X) \subseteq $N\alpha$ -C(X). That is $C(A) \in N\alpha$ -C(X). Therefore $A \in N\alpha$ -O(X). Hence $N\alpha$ -C(X) \subseteq $N\alpha$ -O(X). Thus $N\alpha$ -O(X) = $N\alpha$ -C(X).

Sufficiency: Suppose that $N\alpha$ -O(X) = $N\alpha$ -C(X). Let $A \subseteq U$ and U be a NOS in (X, τ) . Then

$U \in N_{\square}\text{-O}(X)$ and $N_{\square}\text{Cl}(A) \subseteq N_{\square}\text{Cl}(U) = U$, since $U \in N_{\square}\text{-C}(X)$, by hypothesis. Therefore A is an $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in X .

Proposition 3.27: If A is a NOS and a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in (X, τ) , then A is a NROS in (X, τ) .

Proof: Let A be a NOS and a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in (X, τ) . Then A is a $N_{\square}\text{-CS}$ in X . Now $N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(A)) \square N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(A))) \square A$. Since A is a NOS, $A = N\text{Int}(A) \square N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(A))$. Hence $N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(A)) = A$ and A is a NROS in X .

Definition 3.28: A NS A in (X, τ) is a neutrosophic Q-set (NQ-S) in X if $N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(A)) = N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(A))$.

Proposition 3.29: For a NOS A in (X, τ) , the following conditions are equivalent:

- (i) A is a NCS in (X, τ) ,
- (ii) A is a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ and a NQ-S in (X, τ) .

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Since A is a NCS, it is a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in (X, τ) . Now $N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(A)) = N\text{Int}(A) = A = N\text{Cl}(A) = N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(A))$, by hypothesis. Hence A is a NQ-S in (X, τ) .

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Since A is a NOS and a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in (X, τ) , by Theorem 3.27, A is a NROS in (X, τ) . Therefore $A = N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(A)) = N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(A)) = N\text{Cl}(A)$, by hypothesis. Hence A is a NCS in (X, τ) .

Proposition 3.30: Let (X, τ) be a NTS. Then for every $A \in N_{\square}\text{O}(X)$ and for every $B \in \text{NS}(X)$, $N_{\square}\text{Int}(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$ implies $B \in N_{\square}\text{O}(X)$.

Proof: Let A be any $N_{\square}\text{OS}$ of X and B be any NS of X . By hypothesis $N_{\square}\text{Int}(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$. Then $C(A)$ is a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in X and $C(A) \subseteq C(B) \subseteq N_{\square}\text{Cl}(C(A))$. By Theorem 3.24, $C(B)$ is a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in (X, τ) . Therefore B is a $N_{\square}\text{OS}$ in (X, τ) . Hence $B \in N_{\square}\text{O}(X)$.

Proposition 3.31: Let (X, τ) be a NTS. Then for every $A \in \text{NS}(X)$ and for every $B \in \text{NS-O}(X)$, $B \subseteq$

$A \subseteq N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(B))$ implies $A \in N_{\square}\text{O}(X)$.

Proof: Let B be a NS-OS in (X, τ) . Then $B \subseteq N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(B))$. By hypothesis, $A \subseteq N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(B)) \subseteq N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(B)))) \subseteq N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(B))) \subseteq N\text{Int}(N\text{Cl}(N\text{Int}(A)))$. Therefore A is a $N_{\square}\text{-OS}$ and by Proposition 3.17, A is a $N_{\square}\text{OS}$ in (X, τ) . Hence $A \in N_{\square}\text{O}(X)$.

Proposition 3.32: A NS A of a NTS (X, τ) is a $N_{\square}\text{OS}$ in (X, τ) if and only if $F \subseteq N_{\square}\text{Int}(A)$ whenever F is a NCS in (X, τ) and $F \subseteq A$.

Proof: Necessity: Suppose A is a $N_{\square}\text{OS}$ in (X, τ) . Let F be a NCS in (X, τ) such that $F \subseteq A$. Then $C(F)$ is a NOS and $C(A) \subseteq C(F)$. By hypothesis $C(A)$ is a $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in (X, τ) , we have $N_{\square}\text{Cl}(C(A)) \subseteq C(F)$. Therefore $F \subseteq N_{\square}\text{Int}(A)$.

Sufficiency: Let U be a NOS in (X, τ) such that $C(A) \subseteq U$. By hypothesis, $C(U) \subseteq N_{\square}\text{Int}(A)$. Therefore $N_{\square}\text{Cl}(C(A)) \subseteq U$ and $C(A)$ is an $N_{\square}\text{CS}$ in (X, τ) . Hence A is a $N_{\square}\text{OS}$ in (X, τ) .

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